

A Single Particle Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation with the Effects of Temperature

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In general, in cases of temperature in quantum mechanics, one retains the idea of regular bound state wavefunctions and uses these together with Boltzmann weights in a density expression of von Neumann. In the case of temperature dependent Hartree-Fock methods, the temperature comes into the potential as one solves consistently a system with single particle bound states mixed with the Boltzmann weights (for example in the calculation of the overall wavefunction of a many particle nucleus.) Thus, each single particle wavefunction is modified by temperature because the potential is created by the various single particle states and various configurations of these are available if there is a temperature. The various configurations come with the Boltzmann weight.

Recently, there have been a number of very different calculations, which maximize entropy given by $-d(x) \ln[d(x)]$ where $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction subject to constraints such as $\langle W|H|W \rangle = E$ and $\langle W|W \rangle = 1$. These lead to an equation, similar to the time-independent Schrodinger equation, that is to hold in the case of a temperature, even for a single particle.

In this note, we wish to see if one can picture a temperature scenario while still keeping a cycling picture developed in (1),(2). In such a picture, one considered a single particle modeled by $\sin(px)$ (plane waves) being placed in a potential which stirs up many scattered $\sin(kx)$ each with a weight f_k . A resonance is formed with E ($\exp(iEt)$) representing a cycling through these p plane wave states. In developing this argument, it was noted that $V(x)W(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation could have $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ each expanded as a Fourier series. In such a case, $V(x)$ looked like a distribution of waves which could combine with those of $W(x)$ to great a new overall distribution. In the case of temperature, it is suggested that one might add to the usual potential $V(x)$ an extra temperature dependent potential $\sum_p \exp(-p^2/2mT) \sin(px)$ to model collisions with a "heat bath" at temperature T .

For the case of $V(x)=0$, $T>0$, this potential gives different results from that of a Fermi gas and maximum entropy calculation recently proposed.

Equilibrium and Interactions

Traditionally, one uses von Neumann statistical mechanics when dealing with quantum mechanics, namely one uses:

Density operator = $\sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|$, where $W_n(x)$ is the n th eigenstate and E_n the corresponding energy. ((1))

In such a case, there is no interference between different $W_n(x)$ states. (This is not a mixed state system.) If one were to consider this case of no potential, i.e. a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls, one would have $W_n(x) = C \sin(2n \pi/L x)$ and $E_n = (\hbar^2 2n \pi/L)^2$. This would then be used in ((1)). It is interesting to note that the $\sin(2n \pi/L x)$ eigenfunctions are due to $W_n(x) = 0$ at the walls. In quantum mechanics, there is uncertainty in position and momentum, yet the wall is precisely defined as being at a $x=0$ and $x=L$. Another way to perhaps look at this, is to consider that a quantum particle has zitterbewegung type motion, i.e. moves back and forth while moving to the right with an average velocity of v . In such a case, one might argue that in order to have a resonance within the walls, the particle should be able to complete an integer number of cycles. If this is not the case, an equilibrium resonance will not be established. In this case, it seems that interactions leading to thermalization occur only among eigenstates of zero temperature Schrodinger equation. (Temperature dependent Hartree-Fock modifies the zero-temperature eigensolutions, but in a certain way.)

Wall with a Temperature

Consider the classical case of a sparse gas at temperature T . The molecules do not collide with each other, but only with molecules in the wall which is at a temperature of T . Thus, a particle with momentum p would move classically between the walls, but would have its momentum changed at the wall, so that on average it had a probability $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ of being in a state p .

In the quantum mechanical case, a particle bouncing between walls is modeled by $\sin(px)$ (forward and backward moving plane wave) which we argue represents intrinsic zitterbewegung motion. The $\sin(px)$ function can be positive or negative, but for a particle between two walls, this is not important as density is $\sin(px) \cdot \sin(px)$. The positive part may represent the forward motion part of the zitterbewegung cycle and the negative, the negative, as the particle moves on average with v in the forward direction. If a potential is present, however, the forward and backward parts of the zitterbewegung cycle may interact differently with the potential (i.e. with the opposite sign) leading to interference,

Consider now a quantum particle in a one-dimensional space surrounded by two walls at a temperature T . This may imply that molecules in the wall have some motion with a momentum probability of $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. If that be the case, these molecules should also have a CM wavefunction spilling into the region between the walls. In other words, the wall cannot be a sharp point at $x=0$ or $x=L$. The molecules can deliver thermal energy through collisions and so might possibly be represented by a potential $V(x, T)$ where T is temperature. No doubt, the idea that a wall cannot exist at a sharp point in quantum mechanics has been discussed before in the literature.

It was thus argued in (1) that for a quantum mechanical system with no temperature T , one could write:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \int p^2/2m \sin^2(px)] / W(x) + V(x) = E$$

Where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction = Sum over p $f_p \sin(px)$. In other words, a resonance is created. The potential scatters the $\sin(px)$ zitterbewegung particle into different plane wave states through time, but the $\exp(iEt)$ factor of the wavefunction implies the system cycles through the p states in time $1/E$. (see 1). Thus, the picture is one of "plane wave states" or quasiparticle states being scattered by the potential.

If a temperature T is present, one may ask whether a resonance state can be created by the combined action of $V(x)$, the usual potential and $V_1(x,T)$, the thermal potential. In other words, can one write $W(x,T)$, i.e. a temperature dependent wavefunction and find a differential equation with energy eigenvalues which describe the system? If the resonance consists of energy cycling as in (1) with $\exp(iEt)$, one might anticipate a new cycling with a new energy $\exp(iE_n t)$ with $E_n =$ the new energy. If the temperature interactions are much stronger than $V(x)$, then one might anticipate $W(x) =$ Sum over p $\exp(-p^2/4mT) \sin(px)$ while if $V(x)$ dominates completely, $W(x)$ becomes again Sum over p $f_p \sin(px)$. The main argument seems to be that if one wants to have a meaningful $W(x,T)$ for a resonance, then the time factor should be $\exp(iE_n t)$.

In the absence of $V(x)$, one should have a particle in a box. One might argue that with $V_1(x,T)$ present, all sorts of plane waves will be stirred up and one may try to assign a probability of:

$$f_p = \exp(-p^2/4mT) C \text{ where } C \text{ is a normalization constant. ((2))$$

Here $f_p \cdot f_p$ is the probability for momentum p .

It should be noted here that one does not apply the restriction $p=2n \pi/L$ as one is not interested in resonance states as in the von Neumann case. Instead, there is a thermal potential $V_1(x,T)$ existing in space which imparts energy to the plane waves in $W(x,T)$. This potential exists because there are interactions with particles from the wall which can involve interference of different $\sin(px)$'s (plane waves) stirred up, just as in the case of a regular potential $V(x)$. If one applies ((2)), and writes $W(x,T) =$ Sum over p $\exp(-p^2/4mT) C \sin(px)$, then the expectation value of kinetic energy density is Sum over p $p^2/2m \exp(-p^2/2mT)$, just as in a classical gas. Here C is a normalization constant and a a constant needed to make $\int dx \sin(px)\sin(px)=1$.

If one applies ((2)) as the equilibrium condition for the case of no $V(x)$, then one can find that

$$V(x,T) = E_n - [\text{Sum over } p (p^2/2m) \exp(-p^2/2mT) \sin^2(px)] \cdot W(x,T)$$

It is known however, that Sum over $p \exp(-p^2/2mT) \sin^2(px)$ yields a Gaussian so:

$$W(x,T) = \exp(-a(T)x^2) \text{ and } V(x,T) = a(T) - b(T)x^2$$

Thus, it seems that a Gaussian potential would yield $f_p = \exp(-p^2/4mT)$ which in turn gives $f_p \cdot f_p = P(p) = \exp(-p^2/2mT)$.

It has been considered in a series of notes (3) how the ground state of a quantum oscillator is similar to the classical statistical mechanical solution of a gas at temperature T in an oscillator potential. Here we suggest that this oscillator potential might actual model a heat bath (i.e. hot boundary walls) In such a scenario, there is a potential $V(x,T)$ present in space (although as an oscillator potential it becomes high at the walls. This means there is an interaction with the potential and not all of the energy is kinetic energy as in the von Neumann case ((1)). For the classical gas, where one has point particles elastically scattering off of a wall at a precise point $x-L$, one only has kinetic energy.

Case of $V(x)$ and $V(x,T)$ Together

In this note, we suggest that one might try to solve for resonances of:

$$(-1/2m) \text{del}^2 W(x,T) + [V(x) + V1(x,T)] W(x,T) = E_n W(x,T) \quad ((3))$$

With $V1(x,T)$ modeled by an oscillator potential. If $V1(x,T)$ is very small, this will be very similar to a regular $T=0$ problem, while if $V1(x,T)$ dominates, solutions will approach the Hermite polynomials. We are not aware if there is any experimental support in favour of ((3)), but propose it as a possible alternative to maximum entropy approaches currently appearing in the literature. One may argue that using $f_p = \exp(-p^2/4mT)$ is the same as maximizing entropy as one can obtain the momentum Gaussian from maximum entropy techniques, but quantum aspects of interference are also present in ((3)). Furthermore, the solutions of ((3)) differ from those of some maximum entropy approaches proposed in the literature.

Comparison with Other Models

Von Neumann Statistical Mechanics The average kinetic energy given by the von Neumann model and ((3)) are the same. The model ((3)), however, implies an extra potential energy:

Thermal potential energy = $\langle W(x,T) | V1(x,T) | W(x,T) \rangle$ which is the potential energy in the oscillator potential.

The model ((3)) does not restrict momenta to $p=2n \pi/L$ for particles in box with $V(x)=0$ at temperature T , i.e. boundary conditions are not imposed.

The model ((3)) allows for interference between different $\sin(px)$ plane waves stirred up by the hot wall modeled by $V1(x,T)$. This is justified in the way they interact with the thermal path (or hot wall) potential $V1(x,T)$.

Maximum Entropy Models

A number of maximum entropy models (4) exist in the literature. These seem to use the idea of a wavefunction $W(x,T)$ existing for a temperature T and a Shannon's entropy of the form:

$$-k \int W(x) \ln[W(x,T)] dx$$

For (4), a number of examples are considered in their paper. Results from their maximum entropy model do not agree with von Neumann energy $E(T)$ or that of kinetic energy ((3)) for a particle in a box. Von Neumann energy, however, is pure kinetic energy as is $\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p$ for ((3)) with $f_p = \exp(-\frac{p^2}{2mT}) C$. In (4), the Schrodinger equation is altered and so some "extra" potential energy may be included in the calculation of $E(T)$, just as it would be in ((3)) with $\langle W(x) | V_1(x,T) | W(x) \rangle$. The solution of ((3)) for a particle in a box with $V(x)=0$ are analytical, while those of (4) are numerical for the same situation. The numerical wavefunctions of (4), however, look similar to Hermite polynomials, at least at a superficial level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, von Neumann statistical quantum physics has been used for a long time. It is based on a density matrix = $\sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) C |W_n(x)\rangle \langle W_n(x)|$. This assumes one works with eigenstates which are a solution of a Schrodinger equation and not plane wave states which make up these eigenstates, as in the model proposed in this model. It also assumes that there is no interference between the different states $W_n(x)$, again unlike the model in this note.

Recently, several maximum entropy approaches have appeared which attempt to calculate $W(x,T)$ with T = temperature, from a Schrodinger type equation, even for a single particle. Such approaches use the maximization of entropy. In this note, we propose an alternative approach which is based on the idea of a potential stirring up plane waves. For the case of a particle in a box with no potential, we introduce a potential $V_1(x,T)$ which will force the plane waves stirred up to have f_p proportional to $\exp(-\frac{p^2}{2mT})$. This approach allows for interference of plane waves and is not restricted to eigenstates of Schrodinger equation as it is based on plane waves. For the case of a potential $V(x)$, we used the combined $V(x)+V_1(x,T)$.

References

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